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The Relationship between Internalized Stigma and Self-esteem in Individuals with Panic Disorder

Tülay YILDIRIM ÜŞENMEZ¹, Aslan DİKMEN²

¹ Assistant Professor Doctor, Dicle University, Atatürk Health Science Faculty, Department of Nursing, Diyarbakir, Turkey, PhD, RN, tulay.yildirim@dicle.edu.tr, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9979-9654>

² Master Student, Dicle University, Health Sciences Institute, Department of Psychiatric and Mental Health Nursing, Diyarbakir, Turkey, RN,

ABSTRACT

This study aimed to determine the the relationship between internalized stigma and self-esteem in individuals with panic disorder. This study was a correlational design. Fourty (40) individuals with panic disorder were included in the study. Descriptive Characteristics Form, Internalized Stigma of Mental Illness Inventory (ISMI) and Rosenberg Self-esteem Scale (RSS) were used to collect data. The total mean score of the individuals with panic disorder were 67.82 ± 6.29 on the ISMI, and 2.80 ± 1.09 on the RSS. There was a statistically negative and strong correlation between ISMI and RSS ($r = -.672$, $p < 0.05$). In the study, it can be said that the internalized stigma of these individuals were at a high level and self-esteem of these individuals were at a moderate level. Additionally, it can be asserted that as the internalized stigma of the individuals with panic disorder increased, their self-esteem levels decreased.

Keywords: Internalized Stigma, Self-esteem, Panic Disorder, Psychiatric Nursing, Mental Health Nursing

INTRODUCTION

Panic disorder is an ongoing illness with relapses and remissions comprising unexpected panic attacks accompanied by physical symptoms such as dizziness, shortness of breath, nausea, and increased heart rate, and cognitive symptoms such as intense anxiety, loss of control, and fear of death (Elkins et al., 2016; Hovland et al., 2015; Wesner et al., 2014). Verbal or non-verbal negative attitudes and judgments towards mental illnesses are expressed by the society in a labeling way.

There are certain problems with mental illnesses that make them difficult to control. One of these problems is the stigmatization of individuals with mental illness by society. Stigmatization refers to a loss of status and social exclusion, in which negative thought patterns about individuals with mental illness emerge (Alptekin et al., 2014). The shame, self-blame, and fear of discrimination that individuals with mental illness experience as a result of being stigmatized by society cause them to stigmatize themselves. For this reason, individuals with mental illness internalize the characteristics attributed to them and come to accept the habitual negative judgments of society (Çam & Çuhadar, 2011; Yeşil & Han Almış, 2016). In addition, a previous study have shown that individuals with panic disorder have moderate levels of internalized stigma (Batinic et al., 2014). The stigmatization experience of individuals with mental illness causes them to feel ashamed of themselves, feel inadequate, avoid social relations, and socially isolate themselves (Sevinik & Arslan, 2020). All these negative situations cause individuals with panic disorder to face many difficulties.

It is known that individuals with mental illness have low self-esteem, lack of self-confidence and feelings of inadequacy (Pujam et al., 2015). Self respect; It is the state of a person loving, valuing and liking himself (Kumar & Mohanty, 2016). Erdoğan stated that individuals with panic disorder have low levels of self-esteem (Erdoğan, 2020). Physical and cognitive symptoms, internalized stigma, etc. experienced by individuals with panic disorder. can affect their self-esteem.

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Increasing the self-esteem of individuals with panic disorder can also contribute positively to reducing the level of internalized stigma, as it can support the process of reintegrating individuals into society. In this respect, our study is important for psychiatric nursing.

The study seeks answers to the following questions:

- Is there a correlation between internalized stigma and self-esteem in individuals with panic disorder?

METHODS

Study Design and Setting

This study was correlational design and was carried out in psychiatry outpatient clinics in 2024.

Population and Sample of the Study

The study population consisted of forty-six individuals with panic disorder. The aim of the current study was to focus on the entire population; thus, no sample selection method was used. Six individuals did not want to participate in the study. The study ultimately included forty individuals with panic disorder. The included participants were individuals with panic disorder (diagnosed according to the DSM-5), volunteered to participate in the study, 18 years of age and above, able to communicate, and had their drug use, drug side effects, and disease symptoms followed regularly by the psychiatrists.

Data Collection Tools

Descriptive Characteristics Form: This form, which was created by the researchers in line with the literature, consists of a total of eight questions, including the sociodemographic characteristics of the individuals (i.e., age, gender, marital status, education status, employment status, presence of a history of mental illness in the family, and duration of the illness).

Internalized Stigma of Mental Illness Inventory (ISMI): This scale was developed by Rister et al. (Rister et al., 2003). A Turkish validity and reliability study was performed by Ersoy and Varan. The Cronbach's α coefficients of the scale were reported as 0.89 (Ersoy & Varan, 2007). The scale has no cut-off point. Higher scores in ISMI mean that the person's internalized stigmatization is more severe. Those who score 0–25 on the scale are determined to have low, those who score 26–39 are determined to have moderate and those who score 40 and above are determined to have high levels of internalized stigma (Ersoy & Varan, 2007). The scale is structured in a four-point Likert-type design (strongly disagree=1 point, disagree=2 points, agree=3 points, strongly agree=4 points) and consists of 29 items.

Rosenberg Self-esteem Scale (RSS): Rosenberg developed the scale. The validity and reliability of the Turkish version were tested by Çuhadaroğlu, who notified a Cronbach's α internal consistency coefficient of 0.89 (Çuhadaroğlu, 1986). It contains 10 questions that are rated on a four-point Likert-type scale. The total score ranges between 0 and 6. The score intervals are as follows: 0–1 = high level of self-esteem, 2–4 = moderate level of self-esteem, and 5–6 = low level of self-esteem.

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Ethical Consideration

Before starting the study, approval from the Ethics Committee of a University (Approv. No: 668409, 2024-5) and legal permission from the hospital where the study was conducted were obtained. Individuals with panic disorder were informed about the purpose of the study and that their information would be kept confidential and that they could withdraw from the study at any time. In addition, the study was carried out in accordance with the Principles of the Declaration of Helsinki and by obtaining written consent from the individuals with an 'Informed Voluntary Consent Form'.

RESULTS

It was determined that 62.5% of the individuals with panic disorder were between the ages of 29 and 39, 62.5% were female, 40.0% were high school graduate, 65% were married, 52.5% were employed, 85.0% had no history of mental illness in the family, and 52.5% had had the illness for 6–10 years (Table 1)

Comparison of the individuals' mean ISMI and RSS total scores according to descriptive characteristics revealed no statistically significant differences associated with age groups, gender, educational status, marital status, working status, presence of a history of mental illness in the family, and duration of the illness ($p < 0.05$).

The total mean score of the individuals with panic disorder were 67.82 ± 6.29 on the ISMI, and 2.80 ± 1.09 on the RSS. According to the total mean score of the scales, it can be said that the internalized stigma of these individuals were at a high level and self-esteem of these individuals were at a moderate level.

It was determined that there was a statistically negative and strong correlation between total mean score of the RSS and total mean score of the ISMI (Spearman correlation, $r = -0.672$, $p < 0.05$).

DISCUSSION

In this study, it was determined that there was a statistically negative and strong correlation between the total mean score of the RSS and total mean score of the ISMI. In line with these results, it can be asserted that as the internalized stigma of the individuals with panic disorder increased, their self-esteem levels decreased. Self-esteem appears to be a core element in reducing the negative effects of internalized stigma on aspects of QOL among people with mental illness (Oliveira et al., 2016). Patients with panic disorder higher levels of internalized stigma had significantly lower self-esteem (Batinic et al., 2014). Internalized stigma may influence the help-seeking behaviors and overall process of treatment, not only for patients with severe mental illnesses, but also for those who have mild or moderate mental disturbances. These diagnostic groups must be paid attention while executing studies against stigma and self-stigma. Otherwise, this kind of discrimination in anti-stigma campaigns may increase the stigmatization of mental illnesses (anxiety disorders, somatoform disorders, and obsessive-compulsive disorder) (Beyazyüz et al., 2015). Individuals with anxiety disorder perceive every diagnosed symptom of an anxiety disorder as a painful stigma which lowers their self-esteem (Ociskova et al., 2013). The results of this study therefore indicate that internalized stigma may be an important factor in the recovery processes of individuals with panic disorder. Many interventions have focused on reducing the psychiatric symptoms of individuals with panic disorder.

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As a side effect of mental illness, individuals may develop the risk of internalized stigma. In addition, this risk can be seen as a major obstacle to the recovery process and realization of life goals for individuals with panic disorder. However, the self-esteem of individuals with panic disorder may protect them against the risk of internalized stigma. With the increase of internalized stigma, individuals' alienation from society, introversion, difficulty maintaining their individual and social roles, and feelings of worthlessness and uselessness may decrease their self-esteem levels. Increasing the level of self-esteem of individuals with panic disorder may improve their ability to cope with the illness by resisting stigma and supporting their social functionality and interpersonal relationships.

CONCLUSION and RECOMMENDATION

It was determined that there was a negative and strong correlation between self-esteem and internalized stigma, and a positive and strong correlation with stigma resistance. The level of internalized stigma in individuals with panic disorder may negatively affect their self-esteem, and many psychotherapeutic interventions can be recommended to increase the self-esteem of individuals with panic disorder and reduce the level of internalized stigma. In addition, multicenter, randomized controlled studies with larger samples are recommended.

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